

Effetti post-incendio sul deflusso nei Monti Pisani

Post-wildfire impacts on surface runoff in the Monti Pisani

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Sommario

Alla luce dei cambiamenti climatici attuali, i quali producono l'aumento delle temperature medie, la diminuzione dell'umidità del suolo e la potenziale riduzione delle precipitazioni, non è improbabile attendersi un aumento della frequenza, dell'estensione areale e della severità degli incendi boschivi, in particolare nelle regioni mediterranee. Gli incendi boschivi rappresentano uno dei più importanti processi di disturbo degli ecosistemi forestati, alterandone profondamente il ciclo idrologico. Nel settembre 2018 e nel febbraio 2019 due incendi boschivi particolarmente estesi hanno bruciato circa 1400 ettari di territorio nei Monti Pisani, all'interno dei comuni di Calci e Vicopisano (Pisa, Toscana, Italia). Un terzo incendio si è sviluppato su un'area di 25 ha nel comune di Vicopisano ad Agosto 2021. Negli incendi sono stati coinvolti sia terreni boschivi sia coltivati con aree estese bruciate con severità moderata o alta. L'orografia montuosa dell'area, unita alla sua vicinanza al mare, porta a notevoli fluttuazioni delle precipitazioni sia in termini di variabilità che di intensità. In aggiunta, la presenza di un substrato a bassa permeabilità, prevalentemente quarziti e scisti, insieme a un'estesa e densa copertura vegetale, rende il sito di studio un luogo ideale per l'analisi della dinamica delle acque superficiali. Inoltre, questi bacini forestali svolgono un ruolo cruciale nella ricarica delle risorse idriche sotterranee della pianura costiera necessarie all'approvvigionamento per un numero significativo di abitanti e attività agricole. Negli anni successivi agli incendi, sono stati condotti numerosi esperimenti sul campo per cercare di valutare le conseguenze di questi due eventi sulle dinamiche e sui flussi idrici locali. Le diverse indagini hanno incluso il monitoraggio a lungo termine dei deflussi, la verifica delle proprietà idrauliche dei suoli e la caratterizzazione chimica e isotopica di diverse matrici idriche. Verrà quindi presentata una sintesi delle analisi a medio e lungo termine.

Abstract

Under the current climate trajectory, increasing temperatures, decreasing average soil moisture and potential reduction in precipitation, it is not unlikely to expect an increase in fire frequency, range extent and severity for the Mediterranean regions. Wildfires

constitute one of the most important natural disturbances in forest ecosystems and in forested watersheds. They can deeply modify watersheds hydrology and water fluxes having an impact on processes such as evapotranspiration, superficial runoff, infiltration, and groundwater recharges. In September 2018 and February 2019 two vast wildfires burnt around 1400 ha of forested territory in the Monti Pisani mountain ridge, within the municipalities of Calci and Vicopisano (Pisa, Tuscany, Italy). A third fire developed over an area of 25 ha in the municipality of Vicopisano in August 2021. Both forested and cultivated land were largely affected by moderate to high fire severity. The area's mountainous terrain, coupled with its proximity to the sea, leads to considerable fluctuations in precipitation both in terms of variability and intensity. Additionally, the presence of low permeability bedrock, predominantly composed of quartzites, arenites, and shists, along with extensive and thick vegetation cover, renders the study site an ideal location for the analysis of surface water dynamics. Furthermore, these forested watersheds play a crucial role in the recharge of the groundwater resources of the coastal plain, which are crucial for the water supply of a large number of inhabitants and agricultural establishments. During the years following the wildfires, many field experiments were implemented to try to evaluate the consequences of these two events on the local water dynamics and fluxes. The different investigations included long-term stream discharge monitoring, soil hydraulic property testing, and chemical and isotopic characterization of different water matrices. A summary of the long-term analysis will be presented.

1. Introduction

Wildfires exert a strong influence on forested watersheds, leading to substantial alterations and disturbance of the hydrological dynamics (Hallema et al. 2017; Smith et al. 2011). Under the current climatic trends, i.e. increasing temperatures, decreasing soil moisture, and potentially reduced precipitations, an increase in wildfire frequency, extension, and severity is likely, particularly in Mediterranean regions (Gould et al. 2016). Thus, it is of paramount importance to extend the knowledge of the hydrologic consequences of wildfires. A substantial body of literature has already explored the effects of wildfires on the hydrology of forested watersheds, spanning along, superficial water dynamics (Shakesby and Doerr 2006), soil hydraulic properties (Beatty and Smith 2013), and groundwater storage (Bart and Tague 2017).

The primary factors driving changes in the overall hydrological cycle are the disruption of vegetation cover and the reduction in soil infiltration rates. These alterations have lasting effects on peak flows, base flows, and water yields, persisting for several years post-fire. (Wagenbrenner et al. 2021). In addition, the recovery to pre-fire hydrological conditions may be not linear with variation of the superficial and groundwater fluxes driven by the increase in

evapotranspiration due to vegetation re-growth (Xu et al. 2022). Thus, the importance of extended monitoring programs after wildfires.

In the last decades, the Monti Pisani ridge area was affected by several wildfires, due to the combination of fire-prone climate and vegetation, and large human presence. In the last 54 years, 75 wildfires (1.4 wildfires per year) occurred in this territory, with a total burnt area of 6173 ha (126 ha per year) (D.R.E.A.M. Italia 2020). In September 2018 one of largest wildfire in the area, started by an arsonist, hit the municipalities of Calci and Vicopisano. A few months later in February 2019 another wildfire developed in the neighbouring area. Overall, the burnt area covered almost 1400 ha of territory with the majority being of moderate to high severity burn. In August 2021, another wildfire burnt around 25 hectares of forested and cultivated land near the village of Vicopisano. Multiple research activities have been started to study the effects of the wildfires in the area and are here briefly presented.

1.1 Study area

The Monti Pisani is a relatively small mountainous ridge of Tuscany (Central Italy) (Fig. 1). The mountainous ridge has an extension of about 150 km², an elevation spanning from 10 to 900 m a.s.l. (average of 230 m a.s.l.), an average slope of about 19°. According to Köppen's classification, the area falls into the climate type Cs, namely humid temperate with summer aridity, and particularly in the subtype Csa.

Fig. 1. The Monti Pisani mountainous ridge, with the burnt areas and the monitored watersheds ridge.

The rainfall regime is sub-Mediterranean, with minimum rainfall in summer and main and secondary maximum rainfall in autumn and winter respectively (Rapetti and Vittorini 2012). The mountain ridge includes two main tectonic units, the Santa Maria del Giudice Unit and the Monte Serra Unit, which in the study area are mainly composed of a thick siliciclastic sedimentary succession with predominant sandstone and siliciclastic phyllite (dated Varisc to Triassic) (Carosi et al. 2005; Lavorini et al. 2006). The arboreal vegetation is mainly represented by *Quercus ilex/Castanea sativa* forests, olive groves, *Pinus pinaster* forests, *Quercus ilex/Castanea sativa/Pinus pinaster* forest, and Mediterranean maquis. The urbanized territory amounts to approximately 11% of the studied area. In the alluvial plain, the predominant soil types are Ultic Haplustalfs or Typic Dystrustepts. At higher elevations, the prevailing soil types are Lithic Haplustepts or Typic Dystrustepts (<http://sit.lamma.rete.toscana.it/websuoli/>). Since 1970, the Monti Pisani area experienced at least 75 wildfires, highlighting its fire-prone features (Mastrolonardo et al. 2022).

The first and largest of the wildfires considered in this work started on 24th September 2018 in the Calci municipality (Fig. 1). The total burnt area was quantified in 1196 ha, mainly of forested and agricultural areas. About 12% of the burnt area was characterized by high severity and 59 by moderate severity (D.R.E.A.M. Italia 2020; Mastrolonardo et al. 2022). The second wildfire started on 24 February 2019 in the municipality of Vicopisano, which burnt around 200 ha of territory (Fig. 1). In both cases, the pre-fire weather conditions were particularly dry, and the wildfire development and expansion were driven by a strong and constant wind. The combination of low relative humidity, strong winds, high temperatures, topography (average slopes of 60%) and fire-prone vegetation caused the rapid spreading of the fire (D.R.E.A.M. Italia 2020). A third and smaller wildfire started on the 14th of August 2021 again in the municipality of Vicopisano and burnt an area of about 25 hectares mostly within a small watershed of mixed forest and olive groves (Fig. 1).

2. Research activities

The paired-watershed method was here applied to evaluate wildfire impacts on runoff dynamics. Comparing burnt watersheds with unburnt control ones, this method allows for the evaluation of wildfire impacts (Clausen and Spooner 1993). The watersheds to be compared were selected to be physiographically similar so that hydrological comparability can be assumed.

2.1 Monitoring networks

Multiple monitoring instruments were deployed in the field. A first monitoring network composed of six hydrometric probes and one automatic rain gauge were installed after the wildfires of September 2018 and February 2019 and collected almost 4 years of stream water stage data (Fig. 1).

A second set of multiparametric probes, acquiring temperature, electrical conductivity, and water level data, was installed on four additional stream sections and corresponding watershed outlets.

Precipitation data were also acquired from the database of the hydrological monitoring services of Tuscany (<https://www.sir.toscana.it/>) (Fig. 1).

2.2. Runoff preliminary results

The rainfall and stream discharge data (Fig. 2) have been used for the evaluation of the changes induced by the wildfires on superficial runoff. Burnt-unburnt watersheds comparison of runoff per unit area for the 2018 wildfire and of runoff coefficient for the 2021 wildfire were performed using the stream discharge data and precipitation data. The preliminary analysis showed increases in the superficial runoff after the fires, as pointed out by the analysis of the runoff coefficients for two burnt-unburnt watersheds relative to the 2021 wildfire and storm runoff volumes for another burnt-unburnt pair relative to the 2018 wildfire (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Precipitation and stream discharge data for one rainfall event at the burnt watershed of the 2021 Vicopisano wildfire.

Fig. 3 a) Runoff coefficient of two burnt-unburnt watersheds for the 2021 wildfire. b) Ratio of areal runoff per unit area between two burnt-unburnt watersheds for the 2018 wildfire.

Fig. 4. Sites of the infiltration tests and boxplot of the saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s).

2.3. Infiltration tests, hydrophobicity

Different surveys were conducted in the burnt areas of the 2018 wildfire and the 2021 wildfires, to evaluate the infiltration rate (Fig. 4) (Mori et al. 2023; Calvani 2019). All tests were performed with a single-infiltrometric ring. Saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s) was derived for each infiltration tests. Three surveys were performed, 3-6 months after the 2018 wildfire, 10 months after the 2021 wildfire, and 4 years after the 2018 wildfire. The K_s measurements were divided into three groups, 3 to 10 months after the wildfire (26 tests), 4 years after the wildfire (33 tests), and unburnt olive groves or forest (32 tests). The mean and standard deviations of K_s values for these groups are 82 ± 86 mmh^{-1} , 833 ± 768 mmh^{-1} , and 455 ± 338 mmh^{-1} respectively. Considering the Olive groves and unburnt forest as a reference, even with most tests executed on cultivated land, the infiltration rate survey showed that the measurements executed between 3 and 10 months after the wildfires had significantly lower K_s values. While 4 years after the fire the K_s were significantly increased both in their mean values and variability (Fig. 4). In correspondence with the first infiltrometric survey (Fig. 4) 20 hydrophobicity measurements were conducted. The hydrophobicity tests had $13' \pm 25'$ mean and standard deviation. No clear correlation appeared between the fire severity and the hydrophobicity (Maxwald 2022), maybe due to the reduced number of tests and the complex effects of fire temperature on the hydrophobicity of soils (DeBano 2000).

3. Conclusions

The wildfire impacts on watershed hydrology is already a mature research area. However, due to the strong hydrologic impact of wildfire, the paramount

importance of the whole forest ecosystem and its benefits and services, and the climate change increasing wildfire hazard, these research programs need to be promoted in the future. Accounting for territorial variability and reliable watershed comparisons will be crucial in correctly evaluating the hydrological impacts of wildfires. This work summarised some of the results of multiple joint research programs conducted by the University of Pisa and the University of Florence on the Monti Pisani area, typically prone to wildfires. The activities showed an increase in superficial runoff induced by the wildfires. Moreover, the reduction of the soil Ks in the months following the wildfires was reported for different burnt areas. However, after some years after the wildfire, the Ks reached again values comparable to unburnt territories.

Further analyses of the multiple collected data are ongoing and will be published in the future. Stream discharge observations, and chemical and isotopic data can shed light on the wildfire impacts on the whole hydrological cycle in the area. Also, differences in minimum rainfall thresholds for runoff generation in the burnt and unburnt watersheds will be investigated.

Bibliography

1. Bagarello V., Di Prima S., Iovino M. Estimating Saturated Soil Hydraulic Conductivity by the near Steady-State Phase of a Beerkan Infiltration Test. *Geoderma* 303 70–77, (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.04.030>.
2. Bart R.R., Tague C.L. The Impact of Wildfire on Baseflow Recession Rates in California. *Hydrological Processes* 31, 1662–73, (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.11141>.
3. Beatty S.M., Smith J.E. Dynamic Soil Water Repellency and Infiltration in Post-Wildfire Soils. *Geoderma* 192, 160–72, (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2012.08.012>.
4. Calvani S. Alterazione dei processi idrologici ed erosivi a seguito di incendio sui Monti Pisani e monitoraggio della funzionalità degli interventi di salvaguardia a scala di versante. Tesi Laurea Magistrale., Università di Firenze. a.a. 2018-19.
5. Carosi R., Montomoli C., Pertusati P.C., Sarti G., Frassi C., Leoni L. Note illustrative della carta geologica d'Italia alla scala 1:50.000. Foglio 273, PISA. Università di Pisa, ISPRA, (2005).
6. Clausen J.C., Spooner J. 1993. Paired Watershed Study Design. Washington, DC (United States): Environmental Protection Agency Technical Report PB-94-154820/XAB; EPA-841/F-93/009, (1993).
7. DeBano L.F. The Role of Fire and Soil Heating on Water Repellency in Wildland Environments: A Review. *Journal of Hydrology* 195–206, (2000). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(00\)00194-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(00)00194-3).
8. D.R.E.A.M. Italia. Piano Specifico Di Prevenzione AIB - Monti Pisani. Regione Toscana, (2020). <https://www.regione.toscana.it/piani-specifici-di-prevenzione>.

9. Gould G.K., Mingliang L., Barber M.E., Cherkauer K.A., Robichaud P.R., Adam J.C. The Effects of Climate Change and Extreme Wildfire Events on Runoff Erosion over a Mountain Watershed. *Journal of Hydrology* 536, 74–91, (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2016.02.025>.
10. Hallema D.W., Sun G., Caldwell P.V., Norman S.P., Cohen E.C., Liu Y., Ward E.J., McNulty S.G. Assessment of Wildland Fire Impacts on Watershed Annual Water Yield: Analytical Framework and Case Studies in the United States. *Ecohydrology* 10 (2), (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1002/eco.1794>.
11. Lavorini G., Carosi R., Pertusati P.C., Montomoli C., Ciampalini A., Franceschi M., Magi S., Sarti G., Ciulli L., Giacomelli S. 2006. Carta Geologica d'Italia. Pisa, Foglio 273. IGMI Firenze. (2006).
12. Mastrolonardo G., Castelli G., Certini G., Maxwald M., Trucchi P., Foderi C., Errico A., Marra E., Preti F. Post-Fire Erosion and Sediment Yield in a Mediterranean Forest Catchment in Italy. Preprint, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.166256297.71210800/v1>.
13. Maxwald, M. Transferability Analysis as a Supporting Tool for the Uptake of Soil and Water Bioengineering Measures in Fire Prone Areas. PhD Thesis, Università di Firenze. a.y. 2018/22.
14. Mori L., Nigro M., Menichini M., Baneschi I., Doveri M., Giannecchini R. Soils Hydraulic Conductivity Tests in Slopes Affected by Fire: An Example on Pisani Mountains (Tuscany, Italy). *Rendiconti Online della Società Geologica Italiana*, (2023).
15. Rapetti F., Vittorini S. Note illustrative della carta climatica della Toscana. *Atti Soc. tosc. Sci. nat., Mem., Serie A*, 41–74, (2012). doi: 10.2424/ASTSN.M.2012.27.
16. Shakesby R., Doerr S. Wildfire as a Hydrological and Geomorphological Agent. *Earth-Science Reviews* 74, 269–307, (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2005.10.006>.
17. Smith H.G., Sheridan G.J., Lane P.N.J., Nyman P., Haydon S. Wildfire Effects on Water Quality in Forest Catchments: A Review with Implications for Water Supply. *Journal of Hydrology* 396, 170–92, (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2010.10.043>.
18. Wagenbrenner J.W., Ebel B.A., Bladon K.D., Kinoshita A.M. Post-Wildfire Hydrologic Recovery in Mediterranean Climates: A Systematic Review and Case Study to Identify Current Knowledge and Opportunities. *Journal of Hydrology* 602 (2021): 126772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126772>.
19. Xu Z., Zhang Y., Zhang X., Ma N., Tian J., Kong D., Post D. Bushfire-Induced Water Balance Changes Detected by a Modified Paired Catchment Method. *Water Resources Research* 58 (11), (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR031013>.